

DESI Mock Challenge VII: halo and galaxy catalogs with the Bias Assignment Method

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the generation of a suit of mock catalogs of dark matter halos and galaxies, aiming at the assessment of precise covariance matrix for cosmological analysis. The set of halo mock catalogs display accurate summary statistics and detailed assignment of halo properties (e.g., velocity dispersion, halo mass), enabling the possibility of using models of halo occupation distribution (HOD) to construct mock catalogs with different galaxy types. In particular, we generate mock catalogs based on HOD for emission-line galaxies, key target for experiments such as the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI). To this end, we rely on the Bias Assignment Method (BAM), in conjunction with the Scinet LIghtCone Simulations of halo mock catalogs (at $z \sim 1$) as training set. We demonstrate the high accuracy of the mocks in the one (abundance), two- (e.g. power spectrum), three- (e.g. bispectrum), four- (covariance matrices of two point statistics), and six-point statistics (covariance matrices of three-point statistics), both in real and redshift space. BAM offers a robust way to produce fast and accurate halo distributions which can be used to generate a variety of multi-tracer catalogs with precise covariance matrices of a number of cosmological probes.

Key words: cosmology: – theory - large-scale structure of Universe

1 INTRODUCTION

The cosmological volume spanned by the nearly 40 million of galaxies (and quasars) planned to be surveyed by the *Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument* (DESI) (Levi et al. 2013; DESI Collaboration et al. 2016b, 2022) imposes unprecedented challenges for both theoretical and numerical cosmology. The precision of the measurements of the statistical prop-

erties of the spatial distribution and weak-lensing signals to be obtained from such unprecedented number of tracers will shed light into the most intriguing features of the standard cosmological model, e.g. the nature of dark energy (e.g. DESI Collaboration et al. 2016a), and primordial non gaussianities (see e.g. Vargas-Magana et al. 2019; Alam et al. 2021). The accomplishment of these goals depends heavily on the access to precise and accurate covariance matrices for the statistical analysis of a number of cosmological probes such as clustering, weak-lensing, redshift-space distortions and baryon

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acoustic oscillations (e.g. Dodelson & Schneider 2013; Taylor et al. 2013; Percival et al. 2014; Paz & Sánchez 2015; Pearson & Samushia 2016; Howlett & Percival 2017; O’Connell & Eisenstein 2019).

This paper is part of current efforts within the DESI collaboration, which aim at establishing a road-map towards the construction of galaxy mock catalogs displaying percent accuracy and precision in a number of statistical properties of the spatial distribution of galaxies (see e.g. Garrison et al. 2018; Grove et al. 2021; Ding et al. 2022). In particular, this article describes the application of a calibrated approach to mock catalogs, the so-called Bias Assignment Method (BAM hereafter Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2019). While a number of approaches of different nature have been designed with this same goal (see e.g., Scoccimarro & Sheth 2002; Sousbie et al. 2008; Schneider et al. 2011; Kitaura et al. 2014; White et al. 2014; Chuang et al. 2015; Avila et al. 2015; Stein et al. 2019), the need for fast and accurate solutions to the issue of covariance matrices has motivated the design of the so-called *calibrated methods*. Among these we find EZmocks (Chuang et al. 2015) and PATCHY (Kitaura et al. 2014), which have been shown to generate accurate galaxy mock catalogs for clustering analysis (see e.g. Kitaura et al. 2016; Zhao et al. 2021) and tested for forthcoming missions (see e.g. Lippich et al. 2019; Blot et al. 2019; Colavincenzo et al. 2018). Compared to these aforementioned methods, BAM represents a step forward both in precision and efficiency, and has been shown to provide accurate covariance matrices for halo power spectrum, when learning from large-volume references and using dark matter halos as main dark matter tracers (Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2020).

In this work we extend the methodology of BAM to the generation of ensembles of halo catalogs with phase-space coordinates and intrinsic properties (such as virial mass and velocity dispersion). Furthermore, we implement a halo-occupation distribution (HOD) framework (e.g., Cooray 2002; Cooray & Sheth 2002; Berlind & Weinberg 2002; Kravtsov et al. 2004) to populate these halos with galaxies, in particular, emission line galaxies (ELG), key target for the DESI galaxy redshift survey (e.g., Raichoor et al. 2020). The strategy envisaged for BAM allows to implement more approaches to populate dark matter halos with galaxies, such as the sub-halo abundance matching (SHAMs) (see e.g. Vale & Ostriker 2004; Kravtsov et al. 2004; Conroy et al. 2006; Favole et al. 2016), as well as the generation of galaxy cluster catalogs (see e.g. Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2012) relying on different halo properties (Hearin et al. 2016; Wechsler & Tinker 2018). This provides a high flexibility at the time of producing mock catalogs for a variety of multi-tracer analysis (see e.g. Hamaus et al. 2012; Abramo & Leonard 2013; Abramo et al. 2016; Wang & Zhao 2020; Zhao et al. 2021) from a number of experiments. Indeed, BAM is expected to provide halo and galaxy mock catalogs for a number of current galaxy redshift surveys, such as DESI (Levi et al. 2013), EUCLID (Amendola et al. 2016), J-PAS (Benitez et al. 2014), and the Nancy Grace Roman Space telescope (Spergel et al. 2015).

The outline of this paper is as follows. In §2 we describe the BAM approach to calibrate the halo bias. In §2.3 we describe the reference N -body simulation and the different models of halo-bias used in this work. Section §2.7 depicts the methodology used to learn the halo bias while §3 is devoted to the construction of halo catalogs. In §4 we present the

HOD model to generate galaxy catalogs and describe the main statistical properties of the resulting ensemble. We end with conclusions and a list of potential developments towards the improvement of the method.

2 THE BIAS ASSIGNMENT METHOD

BAM (Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2019; Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2020) represents the most recent bias-mapping techniques aiming at generating fast and accurate mock catalogs of dark matter tracers. The method has been shown to generate ensembles of dark matter halo catalogs (in the form of number counts) with percent accuracy both at the level of the two- and three-point statistics (see e.g. Pellejero-Ibañez et al. 2020), and has been also applied in the context of hydro-simulations (see e.g. Sinigaglia et al. 2021a,b). This work represents the first attempt to generate halo and galaxy catalogs with phase-space coordinates and intrinsic properties.

2.1 The ingredients of BAM

The BAM machinery relies on a number of ingredients, mainly related to input and outputs from detailed N -body simulations. These can be enumerated as follows:

(i) **Initial conditions** (IC hereafter) of the reference N -body simulation, identified with a particular seed. These IC’s are represented by a initial density field built with a resolution much lower than the original resolution used by the N -body run. A sub-set of these IC corresponds to the down-sampled version of the original ones evolved by the N -body simulation to redshifts at which halo catalogs are provided.

(ii) A set of few **dark matter halo catalogs** whose seeds correspond to the sub-set of the full sets of IC previously described. Ideally, this set must contain a number of intrinsic properties that will be used for the assignment of galaxies by means of a e.g, HOD prescription.

(iii) **An approximated gravity solver** (or surrogate) to evolve, in a fast way, the low-resolution IC to the redshift of the tracer catalog.

Provided the set of ingredients previously presented, the generation of galaxy mock catalogs in BAM is performed in four stages. Explicitly:

(i) **Stage I: Calibration**: learning process in which the halo-bias and BAM-kernel are calibrated using the two-point statistics of the reference as cost function.

(ii) **Stage II: Halo mock production**: generation of independent halo number count fields through the sampling of independent dark matter density fields using halo-bias.

(iii) **Stage III: Phase-space coordinates and properties**: (a), assignment of position, (b) velocities and (c) intrinsic properties to dark matter halos

(iv) **Stage IV: Galaxy catalogs**: implementation of an HOD model to populate dark matter halos with galaxies.

We shall cover each of these steps throughout this article. To facilitate the understanding of the processes involved in the method, we have depicted the different steps as a flow chart in Fig.1.

Figure 1. Flow-chart representing the different stages involved in the generation of galaxy mock catalogs with BAM described in §2.1. The process is mainly divided in two sections, *Learning Phase* and *Mock Production*. In the *Learning Phase*, a number of kernels and halo bias are calibrated from different realizations of the reference simulation, and stacked to generate one version of kernel and bias used at the *Mock Production* phase. The different colors in the arrows indicate the different stages involved in the process (e.g, calibration, generation of independent halo number counts, assignment of halo properties, construction of galaxy catalogs).

2.2 The halo-bias in BAM

The halo bias is a quantity of paramount relevance for the understanding of galaxy clustering, as it represents the midpoint between the distribution of light (galaxies) and the distribution of the underlying dark matter. It is very well established now that halo-bias has to be modelled beyond the standard linear scale independent scheme: scale dependencies induced by the process of halo formation, the nonlinear evolution of the dark matter density field (see e.g Matsubara 1999; Sigad et al. 2000; Somerville et al. 2001; Smith et al. 2007; Tinker et al. 2010; Valageas 2011; Pollack et al. 2012; Sheth et al. 2013; Ahn et al. 2015; Han et al. 2019; Nasirudin et al. 2019), and the discrete presentation of halo and matter

density fields generalizes the concept of halo-bias to a non-local and stochastic quantity (see e.g., Fry & Gaztanaga 1993; Tegmark & Peebles 1998; Dekel & Lahav 1999; Blanton 2000; Simon 2005). Our algorithm captures these notions and assumes that the number-counts of dark matter halos in a cell of volume ∂V depends on a set of properties $\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\}$ of the underlying dark matter density field interpolated on a cells of the same volume ∂V . As such, the halo-bias is defined as a multi-dimensional histogram representing the joint probability distribution of the number of reference halos N_h^{ref} in a cell and the set of \mathcal{N}_p properties of the underlying density field. This is normalized by the distribution of such properties to obtain a conditional distribution function $\mathcal{B}(N_h | \Theta_{\text{dm}})_{\partial V}$, ex-

pressed as

$$\mathcal{B}(N_h|\Theta_{\text{dm}})_{\partial V} \equiv \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{cells}}} \mathbf{1}_{N_h}(N_h(\mathbf{r}_i)) \prod_{\kappa=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{1}_{\gamma_\kappa}(\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}(\mathbf{r}_i)\}_\kappa)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{cells}}} \prod_{\kappa=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{1}_{\gamma_\kappa}(\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}(\mathbf{r}_i)\}_\kappa)}, \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma_\ell \equiv [\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\}_\ell - \Delta_\ell/2, \{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\}_\ell + \Delta_\ell/2)$ represents the set of bins (of width Δ_ℓ) defined for the ℓ -th property of the density field, with $\mathbf{1}_A(x)$ as the *indication function*: $\mathbf{1}_A(x) = 1$ if $x \in A$, 0 otherwise. Note that the conditional probability distribution \mathcal{B} carries no information on the phases of the density fields, and hence represents an ideal statistical quantity that can be learned and mapped into a different realization of the dark matter density field. Equation Eq. (1) is an approximation (or estimator) to the true underlying halo-bias, and ignores key aspects thereof, such as the effects of the mass assignment and correlation between pairs in different property-bins, among others. The impact of these effects in the measurement of the halo-bias are captured (and corrected for) within the iterative process, as will be discussed in §2.7.

2.3 Training set: N-body simulation

We use the `Scinet LightCone Simulations` (SLICS hereafter) described by Harnois-Déraps et al. (2018), which consists an ensemble of cosmological N -body simulations run in a comoving box with of $L_{\text{box}} = 505 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$ side, following the non-linear evolution of 1536^3 particles on a mesh with 3072^3 cells, from an initial redshift of $z_{\text{ini}} = 120$ down to $z = 0$. In this work we use the output at $z = 1.04$. The corresponding halo catalogs consist on a set of virialized objects detected identified using a spherical overdensity algorithm (see e.g. Harnois-Déraps et al. 2013). We have used a set of 80 realizations of SLICS halo catalogs¹ to assess the accuracy of our mocks, in terms of two and three point statistics. A subset (of maximum 27 randomly selected² references) is also used as part of the training set from which BAM can learn the halo-bias (described in §2.7). The halo-mass resolution of the SLICS is $\sim 5.7 \times 10^{10} M_\odot h^{-1}$, which corresponds to halos with nearly 20 dark matter particles. We have imposed a somewhat more conservative minimum halo-mass of $2 \times 10^{11} M_\odot h^{-1}$, which agrees with the expected mass-cut at which dark matter halos can host ELG's (see e.g. Alam et al. 2020). Number counts are generated over a mesh with our fiducial resolution of 192^3 using the nearest grid-point mass assignment (Hockney & Eastwood 1988). Although the halo finder algorithm allows for the determination of different halo properties (e.g. mass, spin, concentration, velocity dispersion), the current set of reference catalogs involves only the virial mass and the velocity dispersion, along with halo coordinates and peculiar velocities, obtained from the position of the density used to identify each halo. These quantities are sufficient to apply an HOD prescription and populate halos with central and satellite galaxies. Notice that the method can be applied to reference halo catalogs built with different halo finders (see e.g. Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2020).

¹ This corresponds to the available number of of initial conditions with the corresponding halo catalogs, and represents a reasonable number of realizations to compute covariance matrices for comparison purposes.

² The reason behind this figure will be explained in §3.2.

2.4 Initial Conditions

The initial conditions of the SLICS consist of a distribution of dark matter particles with positions derived from the Zeldovich displacement of cell-centred particles computed based on a linear power spectrum evaluated at $z_{\text{ini}} = 120$. Given that the Lagrangian position \mathbf{q} of the particles are displaced from a regular distribution \mathbf{q}_0 , the linear density field can be obtained by obtaining the displacement field $\Psi_Z(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q}_0$ computed on a $N_{\text{HR}}^3 = 1536^3$ lattice. Accordingly, the high-resolution (HR) initial density field is then obtained from the negative divergence of the displacement field, $\delta_{\text{IC}}^{\text{HR}}(\mathbf{q}) = -\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \cdot \Psi_Z(\mathbf{q})$. To reduce the resolution to our adopted value of $N_{\text{LR}}^3 = 192^3$ cells, we apply an ideal (real) low-pass filter $\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k})$ (which preserves the phase and amplitude of the original field). The low resolution density field is computed as the inverse Fourier transform of the function $\delta_{\text{IC}}^{\text{HR}}(\mathbf{k})\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k})e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{\Lambda}}$, where we introduce an isotropic shift of the form $\mathbf{\Lambda} = (\Delta_{\text{LR}}/2 - \Delta_{\text{HR}}/2)\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ (with e.g. $\Delta_{\text{HR}} \equiv L_{\text{box}}/N_{\text{HR}}$), which for the current set-up amounts to $|\mathbf{\Lambda}| \sim 1.15 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$. Correcting for this shift is of paramount relevance to avoid degrading the cross-correlation (and the measurements of halo bias) between the low resolution initial condition and the halo catalog associated to the same seed.

At this resolution, the volume of the SLICS yields regular cells with volume of $\partial V \sim (2.6 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1})^3$ and a Nyquist frequency of $\sim 1.2h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. For comparison against the reference simulation, and according to DESI scientific requirements, we adopt a maximum wavenumber of $\sim 0.4h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, which amounts to $\sim 30\%$ of the Nyquist frequency. At those scales, mass assignment effects inherent to the interpolation of halos in a mesh are expected to be negligible (see e.g. Jing 2005).

2.5 Fast gravity solver

The BAM algorithm relies on a combined Lagrangian and Eulerian perturbation theory approach, dubbed Augmented Lagrangian perturbation theory (ALPT hereafter; see Kitaura & Hess 2013; Kitaura et al. 2014), to map the initial conditions represented by Lagrangian coordinates \mathbf{q} (regularly spaced points at redshift at z_{ini}) into final (Eulerian) comoving coordinates $\mathbf{r}(z)$ via $\mathbf{r}(z) = \mathbf{q} + \Psi(\mathbf{q}, z)$, where $\Psi(\mathbf{q}, z)$ represents the displacement field. This displacement is assumed to be split in a long and short-range components, $\Psi(\mathbf{q}, z) = \Psi_{\text{short}}(\mathbf{q}, z) + \Psi_{\text{long}}(\mathbf{q}, z)$. ALPT implements the displacement field from second order Lagrangian perturbation theory (2LPT) to model the large-scale (long-range) displacement (see e.g. Buchert & Ehlers 1993; Bouchet et al. 1995; Bernardeau et al. 2002)

$$\Psi_{2\text{LPT}}(\mathbf{q}, z) = -D^{(1)}(z)\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}\phi^{(1)}(\mathbf{q}) + D^{(2)}(z)\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}\phi^{(2)}(\mathbf{q}), \quad (2)$$

where $D^{(1)}(z)$ is the growth factor (see e.g. Heath 1977), $D^{(2)}(z) \sim -(3/7)\Omega_{\text{m}}^{-1/143}(D^{(1)}(z))^2$ (Bouchet et al. 1995). The potentials $\phi^i(\mathbf{q})$ are the solutions of the Poisson equations $\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}^2\phi^{(i)} = \delta^{(i)}$, where $i = 1$ is the linear density obtained in §2.4, and

$$\delta^{(2)} = \sum_{i,j < i} (\partial_{ii}\phi^{(1)}\partial_{jj}\phi^{(1)} - (\partial_{ij}\phi^{(1)})^2), \quad (3)$$

where we use the notation $\partial_{ij}\phi \equiv \partial^2\phi(\mathbf{q})/\partial q_i\partial q_j$. Equation (3) shows how 2LPT takes into account the Hessian of the initial gravitational potential, and thus is expected to develop

Figure 2. Slices of $25 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$ thick through different density fields involved in the calibration of the BAM products and its products. The bottom panel shows the reconstruction of the halo number density field using different models of halo-bias (see §2.6). The rightmost column shows galaxy density field from the reference and from BAM, built by populating halo catalogs with a model of halo occupation distribution (see §4).

the main features of the cosmic-web on large scales. However, provided that 2LPT is not accurate on small scales (see e.g. Kitaura & Hess 2013), its displacement is filtered with a Gaussian kernel $\Psi_{\text{long}}(\mathbf{q}, z) = \Psi_{2LPT}(\mathbf{q}, z) \otimes \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{q}, r_s)$, with a smoothing scale of $r_s = 20 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$ (we have verified that smoothing scales in the range $10 - 20 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$) lead to consistent results).

While ALPT models the large scales using Lagrangian perturbation theory, it relies on Eulerian perturbation theory to model the small-scale clustering signal. In particular, the short-range displacement is written as $\Psi_{\text{short}}(\mathbf{q}, z) = (1 - \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{q}, r_s)) \otimes \Psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z)$ where the displacement $\Psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z)$ is derived within the spherical collapse (SC) approximation (see e.g. Bernardeau 1994; Bernardeau et al. 2002), $\psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z) = \nabla \cdot \Psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z)$ where $\psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z)$ is the solution to the Poisson like equation (see e.g. Mohayaee et al. 2006; Neyrinck 2013)

$$\nabla^2 \psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z) = 3 \left(\left[1 - \frac{2}{3} D^{(1)}(z) \delta^{(1)}(\mathbf{q}) \right]^{1/2} - 1 \right). \quad (4)$$

The regular Lagrangian coordinates are then mapped into Eulerian coordinates using the total displacement

$$\Psi_{ALPT}(\mathbf{q}, z) = \Psi_{2LPT}(\mathbf{q}, z) \otimes \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{q}, r_s) + (1 - \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{q}, r_s)) \otimes \Psi_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z). \quad (5)$$

With dark matter particles evolved, a cloud-in-cell mass assignment scheme is implemented to generate an approximated dark-matter density field (A-DMDF hereafter) on the fiducial mesh. To improve the description of the nonlinear dark matter field with low number of particles, we implement the phase-space mapping technique (Abel et al. 2012; Hahn et al. 2013).

Notice that the method can in principle implement any ap-

proximated gravity solver (with the correct large-scale clustering signal), given that the BAM kernel is meant to correct for missing power towards small scales aiming at generating the correct tracer power spectrum through an learning procedure (to be discussed in § 2.7). Nevertheless, as long as we use the positions and velocities (see §3.3) from the dark matter particles computed from such approximated methods, and the fact that the tidal field (see e.e. Eq. (3)) is a key ingredient of the method, the trade-off between precision, speed and physical content leans the scale towards 2LPT or ALPT over e.g. the Zelovich approximation (see e.g. White 2014, for a review on the Zelovich approximation). Further developments aiming at improving the precision without major costs in computing times are currently under inspection.

Finally, we retain noticeable that provided the size of the fiducial mesh, 192^3 , which is turn the number of dark matter particles evolved with ALPT, the resulting mass of such particles is $\sim 10^{14} M_{\odot} h^{-1}$, nearly five (three) orders of magnitude above the mass of dark matter particles (dark matter halo) resolution of the reference N -body simulation (see §2.3).

2.6 Properties of the dark matter density field in BAM

In order to capture the main ingredients of halo bias, the set of properties $\{\mathcal{O}_{\text{dm}}\}$ used to characterize the halo bias (Eq.(1)) can be divided in local and non-local dependencies. While the local property can be encoded in the dark matter overdensity at each cell, non-local properties (also dubbed as environmental) properties can be extracted from the tidal field tensor $\mathcal{T}_{ij} = \partial_i \partial_j \Phi$, where Φ is the comoving gravitational potential satisfying Poisson equation $\nabla^2 \Phi = \delta_{\text{dm}}$. In particular,

early implementations of BAM used the cosmic-web classification (hereafter **CWC**), which relies on the behavior of the eigenvalues λ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) of the tidal field (see e.g. [Hahn et al. 2007](#); [van de Weygaert et al. 2009](#); [Forero-Romero et al. 2009](#); [Aragon-Calvo 2016](#); [Paranjape et al. 2018](#)) with respect to some arbitrary threshold λ_{th} (fixed to $\lambda_{\text{th}} = 0$ throughout this work). The **CWC** allows to differentiate the behavior of the halo number counts in knots (labelled as \hat{k} , $\lambda_1 > \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_2 > \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_3 > \lambda_{\text{th}}$), filaments (\hat{f} , $\lambda_1 < \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_2 > \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_3 > \lambda_{\text{th}}$), sheets (\hat{s} , $\lambda_1 < \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_2 < \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_3 > \lambda_{\text{th}}$) and voids (\hat{v} , with $\lambda_1 < \lambda_{\text{th}}$, $\lambda_2 < \lambda_{\text{th}}$ and $\lambda_3 < \lambda_{\text{th}}$). Furthermore, it permits to explore the dependencies on the masses M_k of collapsing regions, defined as percolated cells classified as knots (see e.g. [Zhao et al. 2015](#)). This set of properties (hereafter the **TkWEB** model) has been previously explored in other BAM analysis (see e.g. [Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2020](#)), showing that the inclusion of the different cosmic-web types along with the information on M_k can lead to accurate reconstruction of the halo density field.

[Kitaura et al. \(2022\)](#) introduced the implementation of the invariants of the tidal field I_i in the definition of halo-bias used in BAM (where $I_1 = \delta_{\text{dm}}$, $I_2 = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_1 \lambda_3 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3$ and $I_3 = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3$). This approach aims at bridging a phenomenological description of the tidal field (e.g. with the **CWC**) and theoretical models of perturbation theory in which higher order terms can be written in terms of combinations of the eigenvalues of the tidal field.

In summary, we explore the following models for the reconstruction of halo density fields and generation of mock catalogs:

- **TkWEB**: $\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\} \equiv \{f_1(\delta_{\text{dm}}), \hat{k}, \hat{f}, \hat{s}, \hat{v}, M_k\}$. Use the local density, cosmic-web types and the mass of collapsing regions.
- **IkWEB**: $\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\} \equiv \{f_1(\delta_{\text{dm}}), f_2(I_2), f_3(I_3), M_k\}$. Use the invariants of the tidal field and the mass of collapsing regions.
- **TIWEB**: $\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\} \equiv \{f_1(\delta_{\text{dm}}), f_2(I_2), \hat{k}, \hat{f}, \hat{s}, \hat{v}, M_k\}$. Use the cosmic web classification and one invariant of the tidal field.

The functions $f_i(x)$ represent non-linear transformations aimed at improving the extraction of the bias information in each variable $x = \{\delta_{\text{dm}}, I_2, I_3\}$. We use $f_1(x) = \log(2 + x)$ and $f_2(x) = f_3(x) = 2(x^\alpha - \gamma)/(\eta - \gamma) - 1$ with $\gamma \equiv \min(x^\alpha)$, $\eta \equiv \max(x^\alpha)$ and α a free parameter (fixed to ~ 0.11). The form of $f_1(x)$ has the usual form already used in ([Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2020](#)), while the shape of $f_{2,3}(x)$ aims at mapping the (large) dynamic range spanned by the invariants $I_{2,3}$ to the interval $[-1, 1]$, thus simplifying its binning. Other set of properties such as the eigenvalues of the tensor $\partial_i \partial_j \delta_{\text{dm}}$ (see e.g. [Peacock & Heavens 1985](#)) or characterizations of the tidal anisotropy (see e.g. [Paranjape et al. 2018](#)) can be also applied to characterize the bias, as has been explored in [Sinigaglia et al. \(2021b\)](#).

As previously mentioned, the physical motivation behind the choice of these models lies on the fact that not only local dark matter is the main driver for halo clustering, in what is called “local bias”. Several works have already pointed towards the evidence of assembly bias in halos and galaxies (see e.g., [Sheth & Tormen 2004](#); [Gao & White 2007](#); [Angulo et al. 2008](#); [Montero-Dorta et al. 2017](#); [Musso et al. 2018](#); [Xu et al. 2021](#)). This type of bias not only includes the clustering of halos as a function of their intrinsic properties, but also as a function of their environment (see e.g. [Yang et al. 2017](#); [Fisher & Faltenbacher 2018](#)), a dependency that can be covered with approaches such as the **TkWEB** model. Furthermore,

the inclusion of the mass of collapsing regions allows to include short-range non-local bias focusing on regions with a distinct (collapsing) dynamical state.

On the other hand, the implementation of the invariants of the tidal field (i.e. the **IkWEB** model) aims at assessing the halo bias in a more complete fashion. This can be understood from the degree of arbitrariness arising in the framework of the **CWC**, whose characterization depends on the parameter λ_{th} . The invariants of the tidal field do not suffer from this freedom, and hence contain all the information present in the cosmic-web decomposition. Also, and similarly important, the connection of the invariants of the tidal field and the different terms present in a perturbative approach (see e.g. [McDonald & Roy 2009](#); [Kitaura et al. 2022](#)) allows **BAM** to explicitly include a non-negligible signal of non-local bias up to third order in perturbation theory, a signal that is expected to be measured from forthcoming experiments (see e.g. [Goldstein et al. 2022](#)). Finally, the **TIWEB** model aims at using the information from the **TkWEB** adding the information from one invariant of the tidal field, or a function thereof. One of such functions is the so-called *tidal anisotropy parameter* defined as a function of the eigenvalues of the tidal field as $\alpha^2 \propto (\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)^2 + (\lambda_1 - \lambda_3)^2 + (\lambda_3 - \lambda_2)^2$ (e.g. [Paranjape et al. 2018](#)). This property will be used in the assignment procedure for intrinsic halo properties, explained in §3.5.

Along with the models, the total number of bins is also important to assess whether the process can fall into an overfitting regime. This can be simply quantified by the ratio between the number of bins and the total number of cell available. For the three models explained before (**TkWEB**, **IkWEB**, **TIWEB**) and after a series of numerical tests (mainly focused on the convergence of the method, as will be explained in §2.7), our fiducial number of bins yield $\sim 0.9, 2.2, 0.03$ correspondingly, implying that most likely the **IkWEB** model is subject to incur in overfitting. This situation does not arise at the calibration procedure, since the kernel and bias are applied to the same dark matter field these are obtained from. However, when implementing these products on independent dark matter density fields (as will be described in §3.2), the **IkWEB** model will be more sensitive to any difference in the dark matter distribution of the new field with respect to the reference. In that case, the algorithm generates biased estimates of halo power spectrum for some realizations (e.g. those with density peaks not present in the reference) which lead to mode coupling in the covariance matrix of power spectrum.

2.7 Learning phase: iterative procedure and calibration of halo-bias

The learning procedure in **BAM** aims at generating two main outputs, namely, i) the so-called **BAM-kernel**, and ii) the corresponding (multi-dimensional) halo-bias. The role of the halo bias is to assign number of tracers in cells according to the underlying dark matter properties, keeping track of all statistical anisotropies of the latter. The role of the kernel is twofold: on one side, it corrects for any effective large-scale contribution from non-local bias dependencies not accounted for in the set $\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\}$; on the other hand, the kernel corrects for any aliasing effects caused by the representation of the DMF and the halo distribution on a mesh with respect to the original halo finding algorithm used to construct the reference catalogue.

Figure 3. Summary statistics of the calibration procedure in BAM, based on one SLICS realization. Panel (a): Residuals computed from the reference power spectrum and the halo power spectrum at different iterations within the calibration procedure. Absolute residuals (see Eq. (13)) show that the calibration lead to a precise ($< 1\%$) reconstruction of the halo number counts and its two-point statistics, while relative values show that the deviation around the reference is randomly distributed, with a $\sim 0.15\%$ amplitude. The different lines in each case show the behavior under different models (TkWEB, IkWEB, TIWEB) of halo bias (see § 2.6 for details). Panel (b) shows the power spectrum from the reconstructed halo number counts field in each of the halo models. Panel (c) shows the transfer function $\mathcal{T}_i(k)$ computed as in Eq. (11), evaluated at the last iteration of the calibration procedure; the shaded area denotes the 3% deviation around unity. Panel (d) shows the BAM kernel computed using Eq. (12).

Let us now describe the procedure developed in the so-called *learning phase* of BAM. The main scope of the process is to modify the A-DMDF such that, when sampling it with a halo-bias as in Eq. (1), we reconstruct the halo number counts to percent precision up the Nyquist frequency. Let us then focus on the i -th iteration. At this stage the algorithm starts by determining the properties $\{\Theta_{\text{dm}}^i\}$ from a dark matter density field obtained as the convolution of the input A-DMDF with the so-called BAM-kernel (to be defined below) \mathcal{K} , which in turn is the result of the previous iteration:

$$\tilde{\delta}_{\text{dm}}^i(\mathbf{r}) \equiv (\mathcal{K}_{i-1} \otimes \delta_{\text{dm}})(\mathbf{r}) \quad (6)$$

(where $\mathcal{K}(\mathbf{r}) = \delta^3(\mathbf{r})$ for the first iteration). With this new version of the density field, the halo-bias $\mathcal{B}(N_{\text{h}}^{\text{ref}} | \Theta_{\text{dm}}^i)$ is measured using Eq. (1), and then used to sample the density field $\tilde{\delta}_{\text{dm}}^i$ to obtain a new halo number count on the mesh (to which we also refer as to the *reconstructed field*):

$$\{N_{\text{h}}^i(\mathbf{r})\} \sim \mathcal{B}(N_{\text{h}}^{\text{ref}} | \{\Theta_{\text{dm}}\} = \{\Theta_{\text{dm}}^i(\mathbf{r})\})_{\partial V}. \quad (7)$$

The main statistical property adopted as target for the BAM algorithm is the halo power spectrum. This is obtained as an

spherical average of the 3D Fourier transform of the the new halo number count field, $N_{\text{h}}^i(\mathbf{k})$, performed in shells identified with a wavenumber k_j ,

$$P_i(k_j) = \frac{1}{N_j} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \Delta k_j} |N_{\text{h}}^i(\mathbf{k})|^2 - S, \quad (8)$$

where N_j is the number of Fourier modes in the j -th shell (of width Δk_j), and the sum is done over all vector modes with magnitude in that shell. Here $S = 1/\bar{n}$ is the Poisson shot-noise (Peebles 1980) of the reference halo catalog. We then define a power transfer function

$$\mathcal{T}_i(k_j) \equiv \frac{P_{\text{ref}}(k)}{P_i(k_j)}, \quad (9)$$

where $P_{\text{ref}}(k_j)$ denotes the power spectrum of the reference halo catalogue (measured as in Eq. (8)). The sampling procedure of Eq. (7) is performed such that the new HDF not only contains the same number of objects as that of the reference, but also shares its number-count statistics (number-count distribution function).

For each spherical shell in Fourier space, BAM implements

Figure 4. Power spectrum (left) and reduced bispectrum (right) computed from sets of halo number-count mock catalogs (of 80 realizations each) obtained from the calibration of **BAM** using the **TkWEB** model as described in §2.6. First rows show the mean in each case. The second row shows the ratio of to the reference (RTR) and the third row shows the variance in the respective statistics. The shaded area in the second rows denote the 5% deviation with respect to unity.

a Metropolis-Hasting algorithm (see e.g. [Heavens 2009](#)) to accept or reject the corresponding value of the transfer function defined in Eq. (9). As metric, **BAM** uses the quadratic difference of the mock and reference power spectra in units of the Gaussian variance (see e.g. [Dodelson 2003](#)) of the latter (the standardized Euclidean distance). That is, we define a mode-by-mode likelihood of the form

$$\mathcal{L}_i(k_j) \equiv \exp\left(-\frac{(P_i(k_j) - P_{\text{ref}}(k_j))^2}{4(P_{\text{ref}}(k_j) + S)^2} N_j\right), \quad (10)$$

The algorithm maximizes the function $\mathcal{L}_i(k_j)$ by accepting the new power spectrum -and therefore the corresponding transfer function $\mathcal{T}_i(k_j)$, with the probability $p_{ij} = \min(1, \mathcal{L}_i(k_j)/\mathcal{L}_{i-1}(k_j))$. If the transfer at a given mode is not accepted, the algorithm retains the previous accepted value. To express this fact, we define a set of weights $\omega_i(k)$ constructed according to the rejection criteria:

$$\omega_i(k_j) \equiv \begin{cases} \mathcal{T}_i(k_j) & \text{if accepted} \\ 1 & \text{if rejected,} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

These weights are used to define (and to update) the **BAM**-kernel, by multiplying the weights at the current step with

those from the preceding iterations:

$$\mathcal{K}_i(k_j) = \prod_{\ell=1}^{\ell=i-1} \omega_\ell(k_j). \quad (12)$$

The A-DMDF is then convolved with this updated version of the kernel, (see Eq. 6), from which a new iteration follows. Notice that the transfer function defined in Eq.(11) is applied to the dark matter density field, and not directly to the field we are trying to reconstruct. Hence there is no explicit need to define it under a squared root (see e.g. [Weinberg 1992](#)).

The learning (or calibration) phase is considered to converge when the absolute residuals R , defined as

$$R_i[\%] \equiv \frac{100}{N_F} \sum_{j=1}^{j=N_F} |\mathcal{T}_i(k_j) - 1|, \quad (13)$$

(where N_F is the number of spherical shells used to measure the power spectrum) reach the threshold $\sim 1\%$. We have used 300 iterations, although with ~ 150 iterations the calibration has already reached the sub-percent residuals. In terms of computing time, at a 32-threads work station, the calibration procedure (with 300 iterations) takes ~ 1 hour.

In order to verify that the outputs of the iterative process are independent on the realization used as reference, we

repeated this procedure for a number of reference simulations (IC plus halos) available in the SLICS set. In Fig. 2 we show slices through the different density fields involved in the calibration procedure performed with one randomly selected reference simulation. In particular, we show the halo number counts on a mesh (second row) reconstructed using the three halo-bias models described in §2.6.

Figure 3 shows the summary statistics arising from the products of the iterative stage, using different models for the multidimensional halo bias, and using one reference simulation. All the models shown are in position to generate sub-percent residuals in the calibration with (see panel a) with reconstructed power spectra (panel b) within 5% of difference with respect to the reference up to the Nyquist frequency. The models of halo-bias shown display minor differences in their performances when explored at the level of the reconstructed power spectrum, as can be inferred from the panel (c) of the previously mentioned figure, where we show the ratio of the power spectrum from the reconstructed field to the same quantity measured from the reference. Only on the first Fourier mode, the differences with respect to the references are above 2%, while for the rest of the probed Fourier modes and up to the Nyquist frequency, the differences oscillate around $\sim 0.6\%$ percent. We have explicitly verified that similar behaviors are obtained when other realization is used to perform the calibration, displaying the aforementioned large differences on the largest scale. It is key to notice that the fluctuations on large scales are not only a consequence of the small volume, but are also linked to the stochastic nature of halo bias as expressed by Eq.(1).

The differences among the implemented models of halo-bias can be observed in the shape of their corresponding kernel, as shown in panel (d) of Fig. 3. Notice that the definition of the kernel implies that it does not explicitly encode any information on the anisotropies of the halo density field, which is clearly present in the large-scale distribution in the form of a filamentary structure. Indeed, the kernel in configuration space is fully symmetric, although the patterns can change according to the model of halo-bias (and the type of mass assignment scheme). The information of the anisotropies in the 3D halo distribution is instead statistically encoded in the halo-bias, and as such, the model (i.e, the set of properties $\{\Theta\}$) are key to reproducing higher order statistics, as we show below.

In general, the overall shape of the kernel agrees within all tested models: a constant amplitude towards large-scales, with a scale dependency on small-scales. The difference in the large-scale amplitude encodes the different content of information of assembly bias being accounted for as long as different non-local terms are included. That is, the higher the amount of information of halo bias, the closer to unity on large scales. The constant amplitude of the kernel towards large scales is a property that can be used to generate mock catalogs on larger cosmological volumes. This is the subject of forthcoming publications.

3 CONSTRUCTION OF HALO CATALOGS

In this section we describe the steps followed to generate halo number-counts on a cubic mesh, starting from independent dark matter density fields and using the outputs described in

Figure 5. Correlation coefficients of the halo power spectrum obtained from a set of 80 realizations of halo number-counts using the SLICS and BAM mock catalogs, calibrated from different number of references N_{ref} and two characterizations of the properties of the dark matter density field (TkWEB and TIWEB).

§2.7. To compare the summary statistics of the mocks produced within BAM with those from the reference, we make all comparisons with a set of $N_{sim} = 80$ mocks. We will test different models of halo bias and based on the performance of the summary statistics obtained from the mocks therewith constructed, we shall adopt a model of halo bias to generate the final set of galaxy mock catalogs.

3.1 On the halo-bias and kernel

Based on the set of N_{sim} initial conditions described in §2.4, we have generated the same number of realisations of (approximated) dark matter density fields δ_{dm}^j ($j = 1, \dots, N_{sim}$). These are convolved with the BAM-kernel, $\tilde{\delta}_{dm}^j \equiv \mathcal{K} \otimes \delta_{dm}^j$, after which the non-local properties (e.g cosmic-web types) of the resulting field $\tilde{\delta}_{dm}^{(j)}$ are determined. According to these properties, the algorithm populates these dark matter fields with a number of haloes in cells as sampled as

$$\{N_h^j(\mathbf{r})\} \sim \mathcal{B}(N_h^{ref} \mid \{\tilde{\Theta}_{dm}\}_\ell = \{\tilde{\delta}_{dm}^j(\mathbf{r})\}_\ell). \quad (14)$$

Previous analysis with BAM (see e.g. Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2019) have shown that when using reference simulations probing larger cosmological volumes (e.g. ~ 3 times that of the SLICS), only one realization (one member of the reference set) is sufficient to generate an ensemble of number counts with precise summary (statistics up to the four-point statistics). However, numerical tests with the current set-up have shown that this procedure, based on one single calibration (i.e, based

Figure 6. Same as Fig.5 for the reduced bispectrum of dark matter halos in the equilateral configuration $k_1 = k_2 = 0.2h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

on a single realization), can suffer the effects of the relatively small volume of the reference simulation (cosmic-variance). To circumvent this, we generalize the sampling procedure of Eq. (14) and allow each dark matter density field to be sampled with the bias and kernel independently inferred from a number ≥ 1 of reference catalogs. That is, we calibrated N_{ref} halo-bias and kernels from the same number of SLICS references (as shown in §2.7) and construct a total bias by “stacking” the independent halo-bias, along with a kernel, obtained as the average from those of each reference:

$$\mathcal{B}_{\text{tot}}(N_h|\{\Theta\}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_{ref}} \mathcal{B}_j(N_h|\{\Theta\})_{\partial V}, \quad \mathcal{K}_{\text{tot}}(k_i) = \frac{1}{N_{ref}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{ref}} \mathcal{K}_j(k_i). \quad (15)$$

Adding the results of different calibrations as expressed by Eq. (15) is equivalent to increasing the volume of the reference simulation (keeping the same minimum tracer mass and spatial resolution) to an effective value $V_{\text{eff}} = N_{ref}^{1/3} L_{\text{box}}^3$. Notice however that the stacked version of the halo bias will differ from the bias measured from an N -body simulation probing the volume V_{eff} (with same initial conditions), due to the absence -in the former, of super-sample modes (e.g. Rimes & Hamilton 2006; Takada & Hu 2013), evidenced though the underestimation of high density peaks, leading to biased estimates of covariance matrices of clustering probes. For the present case, this is not a problem since we apply the kernel and bias of Eq. (15) to DMDF with the volume of the reference simulation.

Balaguera-Antolínez et al. (2019) also demonstrated that the implementation of a kernel along with its corresponding halo-bias (i.e, the set of outputs obtained from the learning phase with a given IC) is key to delivering halo fields with

accurate summary statistics (e.g. covariance matrix of power spectrum). Hence, the definition of Eq. (15) can be a potential source of inaccuracies, since the resulting kernel \mathcal{K}_{tot} has not necessarily attached a halo-bias represented by \mathcal{B}_{tot} . Instead, it is closer to what we can obtain using a reference simulation with *fixed-amplitude* initial conditions (Angulo & Pontzen 2016); that is, Eq. (15) aims at suppressing cosmic-variance in the kernel while keeping it in the total halo-bias. Accordingly, these two quantities are not physically (statistically) compatible, since the abundance of massive halos (or high density regions) present in the total bias is sensitive to the amount of cosmic-variance of the corresponding IC (see e.g. Heß et al. 2013; Aragon-Calvo 2016): the same cosmic-variance aimed to be suppressed with an averaged kernel. Keeping this in mind, we implemented Eq. (15) to assess whether increasing the effective volume can provide better statistics at the number-counts level. We will discuss the results in the following section.

In appendix §C we present the performance of BAM using larger cosmological simulations generated with IC devoid of cosmic variance (Chuang et al. 2019; Garrison et al. 2018; Maksimova et al. 2021). In forthcoming publications we shall address this subject with more detail.

3.2 Stage II: generation of halo number counts

According to the discussion of the previous section, we have generated N_{sim} halo number count-fields, increasing the effective volume by a factor 2 and 3, i.e, using $N_{ref} = 2^3$ and $N_{ref} = 3^3$ calibrations obtained from the same number of references. To obtain a global picture of the performance of the different characterizations of the halo-bias, we have repeated this procedure for all the models proposed in §2.6. As an example, Figure 4 show the comparison between the summary statistics of 80 BAM mocks and the same number of realizations from the reference set, using the TkWEB model. In general, this procedure generates mocks with a mean power spectrum and variance well within 5% of difference with respect to that from the reference set. We have verified that similar results are obtained with the TiWEB model.

To further assess the level of accuracy with respect to the same statistics from the reference, we use the three-point statistics in Fourier space. In particular, we explore the reduced bi-spectrum (or hierarchical three-point amplitude) $\mathcal{Q}(\theta_{12}|k_1, k_2)$ (Peebles 1980), θ_{12} is the cosine of the angle between the wave-vectors \mathbf{k}_1 and \mathbf{k}_2 ($k_{1,2} = |\mathbf{k}_{1,2}|$), with $\mathbf{k}_1 + \mathbf{k}_2 + \mathbf{k}_3 = 0$. We use estimates of the bi-spectrum to assess precision of the method ³ (see e.g. Pollack et al. 2012; Gil-Marín et al. 2012), using as example equilateral configuration with $k_1 = k_2 = 0.2h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. We remind the reader that this quantity is not constrained in the calibration procedure and hence can be used as a yardstick to determine which of the models (or amount of effective volume) provides the best scenario to generate mock catalogs in the form of halo number counts. In the case of the TkWEB model (Fig. 4), the signal of the reduced bispectrum is mostly within 5% difference with the reference, except for low values of θ_{12} , where the difference can be of the order of 10%. We have verified

³ We have used the code `bispect` <https://github.com/cheng-zhao/bispect>

Figure 7. Example of the distribution of halo peculiar velocities $v = |\vec{v}|$ in one reference (solid black histogram) and one BAM (solid blue and filled histogram) halo catalog, in different cosmic-web types (see §3.3). In all panels the *corrected* histogram is obtained after applying an isotropic velocity correction, described in §3.3.

that the results based on the TIWEB model show in general the same trend.

The correlation matrix $r_{ij} = C_{ij} / \sqrt{C_{ii}C_{jj}}$ (where C_{ij} is the covariance matrix) of the power spectrum for different halo-bias models and number of references used as training set is shown in Fig. 5. We can conclude that the TkWEB model provides an excellent description of the correlation matrix when compared against that of the reference. The TIWEB model display extra-coupling, which tends to decrease with higher number of training references, thus emphasizing the need of larger cosmological volumes when one or two realization are expected to be used as training set. We have similarly

Figure 8. Sub-grid modeling for the assignment of coordinates in phase-space. Coordinates of the random tracers are modulated by the fraction f_{col} such that if d_r denotes the separation between the random and its closest dark-matter particle, the new separation is $f_{\text{col}}d_r$. Velocities are modified in two steps: i), an isotropic density-dependent correction $\gamma(\delta_{\text{dm}})$ applied to the velocities of both randoms and dark matter tracers ($\vec{v}_{r,\text{dm}}^0 \rightarrow \vec{v}_{r,\text{dm}}$), and ii) after collapsing the random tracers, their velocities are modified using the parameters β (direction) and ζ (modulo). The angles α and β are defined on the plane generated by the vector joining randoms and their closest dark matter particle and the velocity of the random particle \mathbf{r}_r .

verified that (as anticipated in §2.6) the IkWEB model displays strong mode coupling towards small scales even with $N_{\text{ref}} = 27$, and hence we discard it for the present applications. Such extra-couplings are likely to be consequence of the overfitting regime in which this model has been applied (as exposed in §2.6) which likely mines the lack of compatibility between kernel and bias as discussed in §3.1.

In terms of three-point statistics, the correlation matrix of the reduced bispectrum -shown in Fig. 6, reveals that the TkWEB model is able to provide excellent estimates of six-point statistics (covariance of bispectrum), regardless of the number of references used in the training phase. This is a key result, since the three point statistics is not part of neither of the metric nor of the cost function in the calibration procedure of BAM.

Based on these results, we adopt the TkWEB model to generate independent realizations of halo number-counts which will be used to generate the final set of halo catalogs as described in the following section. We have used $N_{\text{ref}} = 27$ references, but notice that this particular model model is already good enough to allow us to use the calibration from only one reference simulation.

3.3 Stage III-a: assignment of halo coordinates

To assign coordinates and velocities to the set of number counts obtained in §3.2, we follow the approach of Kitaura et al. (2016) and assign the coordinates of the dark matter particles generated by the approximated gravity solver (§2.5). The sampling of the halo number counts field is complemented with a set of random tracers (e.g., tracers with random coordinates within each cell) used when, at a given cell, the number of halos requested is larger than the avail-

Figure 9. Halo power spectrum computed from the halo catalogs interpolated on a 400^3 mesh, in real ($P(k)$) and redshift space, the latter represented through the monopole $P_0(k)$, the quadrupole $P_2(k)$ and the hexadecapole $P_4(k)$. The main panels show the mean from 80 SLICS realizations (green dashed line) and the mean from the same number of BAM mocks (solid gray lines). The bottom panels show the ratio between the mean spectra from the BAM mocks to the mean from the SLICS. The gray area in the ratios show the 1σ region computed from the means and their respective errors.

able number of dark-matter particles. The fraction of such random tracers depends on the redshift of the reference, and for the current set up it represents $\sim 20\%$ of the total number of tracers.

The use of dark matter particles to sample the halo number count field aims at maintaining a precise clustering signal on scales below the fiducial cell-size. Since the randomly distributed tracers impact the shape of the power spectrum when analyzed at higher Nyquist frequencies, BAM introduces a sub-grid modelling based on the collapse of the random trac-

ers towards their closest DM particles. This collapse is modulated by a fraction f_{col} of the separation between each random tracer to its nearest DM particle. That is, for a separation between a random particle and its closest DM particle d_r , we displace the former towards the latter such that their new separation is the product $f_{\text{col}}d_r$. This is depicted in Fig. 8. Numerical experiments (some will be discussed in §C) have shown that this parameter depends on the redshift and the nature of the approximated gravity solver (Balaguera-Antolínez et al., in preparation). For the current set-up, $f_{\text{col}} \sim 0.35$ provides a good description of the halo power spectrum. Furthermore, the parameter f_{col} can be generalized to depend on halo properties once these are assigned (§3.5).

The top panel of Fig. 9 shows the mean real-space power spectrum obtained from an ensemble of 80 BAM halo catalogs with coordinates assigned as previously described. Each realization is embedded in a 400^3 cubic mesh using the Triangular-Shape-Cloud interpolation scheme (Hockney & Eastwood 1988)⁴. The corresponding bottom panel shows that the accuracy of the mean power from the BAM (with respect to the SLICS) is below 3% up to $k \sim 0.4 h \text{Mpc}^{-1}$.

3.4 Stage III-b: Assignment of halo velocities

The displacement obtained with ALPT (see Eq. (5)) provides the velocities of dark matter particles at their Eulerian coordinates \mathbf{r}

$$\mathbf{v}_{ALPT}(\mathbf{r}, z) = \mathbf{v}_{2LPT}(\mathbf{q}, z) \otimes \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{q}, r_s) + (1 - \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{q}, r_s)) \otimes \mathbf{v}_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z), \quad (16)$$

where the 2LPT velocity field is written as (see e.g. Buchert & Ehlers 1993; Kitaura et al. 2014)

$$\mathbf{v}_{2LPT}(\mathbf{q}, z) = \left[-f^{(1)} D^{(1)} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \phi^{(1)}(\mathbf{q}) + f^{(2)} D^{(2)} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \phi^{(2)}(\mathbf{q}) \right] H a,$$

In this expression $f^{(i)} \equiv f^{(i)}(z) = d \ln D^{(i)}(a) / d \ln a$ are the growth indices computed as $f^{(1)}(z) \sim \Omega_{\text{mat}}(z)^{5/9}$ and $f^{(2)}(z) \sim 2\Omega_{\text{mat}}(z)^{6/11}$ (see e.g. Lahav et al. 1991). The velocity field associated to the SC model is analogously derived as $\mathbf{v}_{sc}(\mathbf{q}, z) = \nabla \psi_{SC}(\mathbf{q}, z)$ where $\psi_{SC}(\mathbf{q}, z)$ is the solution of the Poisson equation

$$\nabla^2 \psi_{SC}(\mathbf{q}, z) = -f^{(1)}(z) H(z) a D^{(1)}(z) \delta^{(1)}(\mathbf{q}) \left(1 - \frac{2}{3} D^{(1)}(z) \delta^{(1)}(\mathbf{q}) \right)^{-1/2}.$$

We assign peculiar velocities to dark matter halos in two steps. First, we generate a velocity field in Eulerian space using the velocities computed with Eq. (16) and implementing an NGP interpolation scheme. It is well known that this kind of approach introduces sampling artifacts, due to the fact that they rely on the particles to generate the velocity field (see e.g. Zheng et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2015), in which case, cells without tracers are incorrectly assigned a null velocity. Alternatives such as the *nearest point* (see e.g. Zhang et al. 2015; Chen et al. 2018) or more sophisticated algorithms such as the Delaunay Tessellation (see e.g. Romano-Díaz & van de Weygaert 2007) or the Kriging scheme (see e.g. Yu et al. 2015) are designed to reduce the spurious bias introduced by these sampling artifacts. We implement a hybrid approach and use NGP as primary method, assigning to empty cells the averaged velocity computed from the first neighbour cells. A

⁴ All power spectra are computed using the COPOWER code, <https://github.com/balaguera/COPOWER>

Figure 10. Top row: Correlation matrix r_{ij} obtained from the BAM halo mock catalogs and the SLICS references computed in real and redshift space, the latter expressed through the monopole $P_0(k)$, the quadrupole $P_2(k)$ and the hexadecapole $P_4(k)$. Bottom row: examples of correlation coefficients r_{ij} at two different wavenumbers $k_j \sim 0.1$ and $\sim 0.32 h \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from the two set of halo catalogs.

second step consists in a tri-linear interpolation of the resulting velocity field at position of both dark matter particles and random tracers (introduced in the previous section).

Figure 7 shows an example of the resulting distribution of the modulus of the halo peculiar velocity $v = |\vec{v}|$ from one realization of SLICS and BAM sets (sharing the same seed). One strong feature arising from this comparison is the difference in the abundance (in terms of v) towards high velocities: above $\sim 300 \text{ km/s}$ the abundance from the BAM halos (i.e. ALPT) is in general under-estimated with respect to the reference. To correct this deviation, we introduce an isotropic correction to the i -th component of each particle’s velocity in the form $v_i^0(\mathbf{r}) \rightarrow v_i(\mathbf{r}) = \gamma(\mathbf{r})v_i^0(\mathbf{r})$, where $\gamma(\mathbf{r}) = (1 + \delta_{\text{dm}}(\mathbf{r}))^\alpha$. Numerical experiments have revealed that $\alpha \sim 0.2$ yields a good agreement in the halo velocity distribution, as is also presented in Fig. 7. We have verified that this correction is indeed a key ingredient to get good agreement in the clustering signal of the BAM mocks with respect to the that form the reference. We speculate that the origin of this correction is linked to the lack of small scale modeling of coherent flows in ALPT combined with the resolution used in the analysis. A more detailed analysis (exploring e.g. redshift and cosmology dependencies) will be presented in future publications.

The second correction to the velocities is applied as part of the sub-grid modelling, focused again on the random tracers (as depicted in Fig. 8). In this case, along with the collapse towards the closest dark matter tracer (discussed in the previous section), we induce a rotation (or collapse) of the random velocities, modifying its orientation (through an angle β) and

magnitude (through a parameter ζ) which can be a function of the tracer properties or local density. In this work we have empirically set this parameters to $\beta = (1 - f_{\text{coll}})(\pi - \alpha)$ if $\alpha < \pi$, and $\beta = (1 - f_{\text{coll}})(\alpha - \pi)$ if $\alpha \geq \pi$, with $\zeta = 1$; that is, we apply a rotation to the velocity vector to align it with the axis connecting the random and the dark matter particle, keeping its magnitude fixed. We have verified that the effect of $\beta \neq 0$ helps to improve the signal in redshift space towards small scales, and leave a thorough study of their impact in the velocity field for future research.

The performance of the velocity assignment in terms of the two-point statistics is presented in Fig. 9, where we show the mean halo power spectrum in redshift space. This signal is obtained by transforming the halo coordinates (x, y, z) along a line of sight axis (taken to be one of the three Cartesian coordinates, e.g. the z - direction) using the distant observer approximation to its redshift coordinate via $z \rightarrow s = z + v_z/(aH(a))$ (see e.g. Kaiser 1987). The clustering in this space is summarized through the Legendre decomposition which, according to the distant observer approximation, can be measured as (see e.g. Hamilton 1998)

$$P_\ell(k_i) = \frac{2\ell+1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \Delta k_j} |N_{\text{h}}(\mathbf{k})|^2 \mathcal{L}_\ell(\mu_k) - \delta_{\ell 0}^K S, \quad (17)$$

where the sum denotes averages in spherical shells, $\mu_k = \cos \mathbf{k} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} = k_z$, $|N_{\text{h}}(\mathbf{k})|^2$ is the three dimensional halo power spectrum, $\mathcal{L}_\ell(x)$ is the Legendre polynomial of order ℓ and S the Poisson shot-noise (as in Eq. 8). We measure the monopole ($\ell = 0$),

Figure 11. Joint probability $\mathcal{B}(x, \delta_{\text{dm}})$ distribution of halo properties x (number counts, virial mass and velocity dispersion) and the underlying dark matter density, interpolated on a 192^3 mesh using a CIC mass assignment scheme and for different cosmic-web environments. Solid lines (and coloured regions) denote contours enclosing 98 and 68% of the total number of cells in a reference SLICS simulation. Dotted lines represent the same quantity obtained from one BAM halo catalog.

the quadrupole ($\ell = 2$) and the hexadecapole ($\ell = 4$) as main statistical probes of redshift-space distortions.

In general, the redshift-space power spectrum probed on scales up to $k \sim 0.4h\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ agree within the 1σ uncertainty region with that the same signal from the reference, as is demonstrated by Fig. 9. Figure 10 shows the correlation coefficient of the halo power spectrum in real and redshift space, computed from the halo distribution. The bottom panels in the same figure shows two elements of the correlation function, displaying a good agreement between the two compared sets. We have verified that this agreement is also observed when realizations with seeds different from the reference set are used.

3.5 Stage III-c: assignment of halo properties

Provided that the BAM halo mock catalogs are to be considered as the building blocks of galaxy catalogs (though the implementation of an HOD model), the BAM algorithm pays

special attention to the assignment of halo properties such as the virial mass M_{vir} and the velocity dispersion σ_v . This step is indeed a critical and far from trivial task within the construction of BAM mock catalogs (Balaguera-Antolínez et al, in prep), given that a simultaneous generation of precise clustering and halo properties would imply the assessment of the distribution of pairs in all possible bins of halo properties, a computation which goes openly against the need for speed in the generation of mock catalogs.

The procedure encoded in BAM finds its motivations in methods developed by Zhao et al. (2015) (see also Chuang et al. 2015), devoted to the generation of luminous red galaxy catalogs (see e.g. Kitaura et al. 2016; Rodríguez-Torres et al. 2016). Those procedures used the properties of the underlying dark matter density field, as in BAM. However, BAM takes the method to a more detailed level, in which more properties of the dark matter and dark matter tracers are considered.

The assignment procedure in BAM (see Fig.1) relies on a hierarchical approach in which a *main property* is defined and

Figure 12. Cumulative halo abundance as a function of virial mass M_{vir} (left column) and velocity dispersion σ_v (right column) obtained in different cosmic-web types (normalized to the number of halos in each cosmic-web type). Error bars indicate the mean and standard deviations computed from 80 realizations.

assigned, followed by the assignment of secondary properties using the scaling relation with respect to the main property. To determine the main property, different options can be considered, e.g., to select the halo property with the tightest correlation with the underlying dark matter density field, or to choose the halo property that drives the main dependencies in the HOD framework. The latter option would lead us to treat the virial mass M_{vir} as main property (which rules the galaxy number counts statistics in the HOD framework), followed by the velocity dispersion (which dictates the redshift space distribution of satellite galaxies). Nevertheless, provided that BAM aims at exploring environmental dependencies (defined through the dark matter density field), we select the first option. Accordingly, while the correlation between virial mass and local dark matter density is of the order of $\sim 28\%$, the velocity dispersion displays a tighter correlations ($\sim 58\%$) with the local dark matter density. This is not surprising, as quantities directly derived from the dynamical properties of the dark matter particles in halos trace very well the depth of the potential wells (see appendix A) and are less prone to ambiguities typical of the definition of the mass of a dark matter halo (see e.g. Skibba & Macciò 2011; Zehavi et al.

2019). In appendix B we describe the methodology implemented for the assignment of properties within BAM. Fig. 11 shows the correlation between different halo properties with respect to the underlying dark matter density field, again for different cosmic web types. We have verified that the scaling relations between virial mass and velocity dispersion agree to acceptable precision with that from the reference set.

3.6 Results

In Fig. 12 we show the halo abundance as a function of the two assigned halo properties from a set of 80 realizations of BAM and the same number of SLICS simulations. There is in general a good agreement, partially broken for tracers with high velocity dispersion in low-density regions (voids), where BAM overestimates the abundance in terms of that particular property.

Similarly, we have also verified that the multi-scaling approach generates better results than a direct assignment of properties. Although this approach naturally attacks the problem of halo-exclusion, it relies on the specification of the different thresholds, and we have checked that the precision of the mean power spectrum of halos is sensitive to such figures, specially on the high-mass halo population. New alternatives are being explored and will be presented in forthcoming publications.

Figure 13 shows the halo power spectra computed from the (mock and reference) halo distribution using a 400^3 mesh. The main panels of the plot shows spectra from the set of 80 BAM simulations and the mean from the same number of SLICS realizations in real and redshift space, in three bins of M_{vir} . The subplots attached to each main panel shows the ratio between the mean power spectra from the two sets, while the area around that curve denotes the 1σ region. In general, the trend shown as a function of the halo mass shows a good agreement between the two sets of mock catalogs. A closer inspection though shows $\sim 5\%$ deviations towards small scales both in real and redshift space, in particular, for the most massive halos.

Figure 14 shows the variance (left column) and correlation matrix (right column) of the halo power spectrum in real and redshift space, for the full halos population. We can read from this figure that in real space, the BAM mocks display larger correlation between modes on small scales, compared to the reference simulation. The situation is mildly better in redshift space, where indeed, the correlation matrix for the quadrupole agrees to well extent with the SLICS simulations. The most significant discrepancy appears when exploring the clustering as a function of the halo mass. In particular, high mass halos display covariance matrices of power spectrum with a strong mode-coupling. Such coupling comes from realizations whose power spectra deviates considerable from the expected mean of the ensemble (i.e. that from the reference suit). These discrepancies find roots in two different aspects of the BAM approach. On one hand, the assignment of halo properties, which turns to be on trivial specially for massive objects, where effects such as halo-exclusion (see appendix A) are not fully modelled. On the other hand, the deviations seen in redshift space are inherited those in real space plus any remaining deviation from the true halo velocity field from the velocity field generated from the ALPT. These two aspects leave room for an optimization in the assignment of

Figure 13. Halo power spectrum computed from the halo catalogs interpolated on a 400^3 mesh, in three different halo-mass ranges (columns) with the real space (first row), monopole (second row), quadrupole (third row) and hexadecapole (fourth row). The main panels show the mean from 80 SLICS realizations (green dashed line) and the same number of BAM mocks (solid gray lines). The bottom panels show the ratio between the mean spectra from the BAM mocks to the mean from the SLICS. The gray area in the ratios show the 1σ region computed from the means and their respective errors.

coordinates, velocities and properties of the halo population, specially towards small scales.

With the procedures described in the previous sections, we have generated 760 mock halo catalogs based on the same number of initial conditions. One of the great advantages of the method is the low computing time it requests: the generation of this set of halo catalogs has been achieved in ~ 2 days (~ 4 minutes per mock), using a work-station with 128 threads and 256 Gb of ram memory.

4 STAGE IV: CONSTRUCTION OF GALAXY CATALOGS

One of the main advantages of BAM is its capability to provide catalogs of different dark matter tracers, all sharing the same underlying dark matter and halo distribution. This is key to provide covariance matrices for multi-tracer analysis (see e.g. Hamaus et al. 2012; Abramo & Leonard 2013; Abramo et al. 2016; Wang & Zhao 2020; Zhao et al. 2021). While this is not an unique feature of this method (see e.g. Zhao et al. 2021), it represents an improvement compared to approaches that need to be calibrated with a particular galaxy population.

To assign galaxies to the dark matter halos of BAM, we have

implemented the HOD prescription based on the *High mass quenched* model (see e.g. Alam et al. 2020), which describes the abundance of emission line galaxies (ELG) in dark matter halos (see e.g. Gonzalez-Perez et al. 2018). This model suppresses the probability for the central ELG galaxies to be found in very massive dark matter halos. In particular, the probability for a halo of mass M_{vir} to host a central ELG can be expressed as

$$\langle N_c | M_{\text{vir}} \rangle = A \phi(M_{\text{vir}}) \Phi(\mathcal{M}) + \frac{1}{2Q} \left[1 + \text{erf} \left(\log_{10} \left[\frac{M_{\text{vir}}}{M_c} \right]^{1/\sigma_M} \right) \right] \quad (18)$$

where $\phi(x) = N(\log_{10} M_c, \sigma_M)$, $\mathcal{M} \equiv \gamma M_{\text{vir}}$, $\Phi(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x \phi(x) dx$ and $A = 2(p_{\text{max}} - 1/Q) / \max(2\phi(x)\Phi(x))$. Q denotes the quenching efficiency, p_{max} controls the saturation level of occupancy, M_c is the cut-off mass for ELG which determines the maximum of the occupation distribution. The number of ELG satellites is modelled as a power-law with an lower cut-off:

$$\langle N_s | M_{\text{vir}} \rangle = \left(\frac{M_{\text{vir}} - \kappa M_c}{M_1} \right)^\alpha, \quad (19)$$

where M_1 is a characteristic satellite mass, while the parameter κ defines a cut-off mass (in units of M_c) below which the

Figure 14. Left column: ratios between the variance of power spectrum from the BAM mocks to that measured from the SLICS in different halo mass bins. Right column: correlation coefficients obtained from the BAM halo mock catalogs and the SLICS references computed in real and redshift space, the latter expressed through the monopole $P_0(k)$, the quadrupole $P_2(k)$ and the hexadecapole $P_4(k)$. Three bins of halo mass are shown (rows).

Figure 15. Mean number of galaxies (centrals and satellites) from the BAM and SLICS ensembles, as a function of host halo mass. The points with error bars denote the mean and variance from each ensemble.

occupancy of satellites drops to zero. The satellites are distributed within dark matter halos following a NFW density profile (Navarro et al. 1996). On the other hand, the random components of the velocities of the satellite galaxies are derived from a normal distribution, $v^s \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_v)$. The total velocity of the satellite galaxies is then given by the sum of the halo peculiar velocity of the parent halos and the random component. The velocities of the central galaxies are the same as that of their parent halos.

The HOD prescription of Eqs. (18) and (19) has been simultaneously applied to the SLICS and BAM halos to obtain their respective galaxy catalogs (see Alam et al. 2020, for the set of parameter $\{Q, \gamma, M_c, \kappa, \alpha, \sigma_M, M_1\}$). The performance of the BAM galaxy mocks in terms of the galaxy occupation distribution is presented in Fig. 15, where we observe how the larger deviations with respect to the reference are embodied in satellite population at the high-halo mass end ($\sim 60\%$ difference at $M_{\text{vir}} \sim 4 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot} h^{-1}$, mass scale below which $\geq 99\%$ of the sample is contained).

Let us now summarize the performance of the BAM galaxy mock catalogs through different statistical probes.

- *Fourier space:* Figure 16 shows the power spectrum for satellites, centrals and the full galaxy population, both in real and redshift space. The most noticeable difference in real space comes from the clustering of satellites, which on small scales are directly probing the density profile of the dark matter halo (see e.g. Cooray & Sheth 2002). Since the two sets of mocks share the same density profile (by construction), the differences in the clustering pattern can be traced back to the

Figure 16. Galaxy power spectrum computed from the halo catalogs interpolated on a 400^3 mesh, split in centrals, satellites and the full galaxy population (columns) with the real space (first row), monopole (second row), quadrupole (third row) and hexadecapole (fourth row). Panels are interpreted as in Fig. 13.

assignment of halo masses, as this is a key property shaping the mass-concentration relation.

Similarly inherited from the parent halo population, the galaxy redshift-space power spectrum displays a lack of power towards small scales. Notice that, contrary to the halo population in which such deviations can be solely tackled from the velocity field of the approximated gravity solver, at this stage we must also add -on top of the velocity field of the dark matter particles, the information of the halo properties used to derive galaxy coordinates in phase-space.

Figures 17, 18 and 19 show the variance and the correlation matrix of the galaxy mock catalogs, split in the two types of population and in different bins of (host) halo mass. In general, the covariance matrices show good agreement when compared against the reference. The extra-correlation at the high halo-mass bins is inherited from the parent halo distribution but only embodied within the statistics of the satellite population. The behavior of the correlation matrices for central galaxies (in all host-mass bins) contrasts with that from the parent halo distribution, as it lacks of the extra mode coupling presented in Fig. 18. The reason for this is that, as pointed out before, the HOD model applied suppresses the abundance of central ELG in high masses halos, hence avoiding the possible deviations coming from the combination of

cosmic-variance and inaccuracies in the kernel-bias connection (see §2).

- *Configuration space:* we measure the standard correlation function (Peebles 1980) in real and redshift space (the latter similarly represented by the multipole decomposition) based on the natural estimator (e.g. Kerscher et al. 2000) $\xi(s, \mu) + 1 = DD(s, \mu)/RR(s, \mu)^5$, where $DD(s)$ ($RR(s)$) is the number of galaxy (random) pairs at a separation s in redshift space, and $\mu = \hat{z}$ (according to the distant observer approximation, see § 3.4). The multipole decomposition of the two-point correlation function is obtained as a Legendre decomposition, in analogy to Eq. (17). Figure 20 shows the comparison of the two-point correlation function of the two data sets (see e.g. Favole et al. 2017, for a clustering analysis of ELG). The picture observed in Fourier space (see Fig.16) is accordingly replicated here, in which a mild systematic bias ($\sim 5\%$) can be observed in the quadrupole, though not statistically significant. The real space correlation function and its monopole in redshift space agrees very well with that of the reference. It is of paramount relevance for the quality validation of this suit

⁵ We measure the correlation function using the publicly available code at <https://github.com/cheng-zhao/FCFC>, Zhao et al. (2021)

Figure 17. Same as Fig. 14 for the galaxy population.

Figure 18. Same as Fig. 14 for the central galaxy population.

Figure 19. Same as Fig. 14 for the satellite galaxy population.

Figure 20. Galaxy correlation function in real space $\xi(r)$ (top panel) and redshift space in the form of monopole $\xi_0(s)$, quadrupole $\xi_2(s)$ and hexadecapole $\xi_4(s)$. The solid line and shaded area denotes respectively the mean and sample variance from the SLICS simulation.

to show how the position and the amplitude of the baryonic acoustic peak is well preserved in the BAM mocks.

- *Marked statistics:* we can jointly assess the clustering properties and the quality of the assignment of halo properties using marked statistics in Fourier space (see e.g. Balaguera-Antolínez 2014) or in configuration space (see e.g. Sheth 2005; Sheth et al. 2005; Skibba et al. 2006; Satpathy et al. 2019). The marked correlation function can be regarded as measure of the clustering of a given property (mark), de-

defined as $\mathcal{M}_\alpha(s) = WW_\alpha(s)/DD(s)$ where $WW_\alpha(s)$ represents the count pair of galaxies weighted with a given property α at separation s . Figure 21 shows the galaxy marked correlation function in real and redshift space, using the halo mass, velocity dispersion as marks, as obtained from the two suits of mocks. In general, the trend followed by the measurements from the two ensembles is consistent, showing how the BAM mocks can properly encode the information of galaxy bias as a function of different properties. Statistically significant differences are sizable when the halo mass is the marked under inspection, specially on small separations, evidencing the trends observed in terms of power spectrum of Fig. 16.

- *Statistical compatibility with the reference suit:* we have verified the statistical compatibility between the two set of mock catalogs by means of a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (e.g. Press et al. 2002) based on the χ^2 distributions of power spectra. The test, displaying p -values of ~ 0.3 , forecasts precise and accurate results (compared to those obtained from the reference N -body simulation) when the set of BAM mocks are subject to likelihood analysis (Chuang et al., in preparation).

5 DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented the construction of galaxy mock catalogs based on the Bias Assignment Method (BAM) (Balaguera-Antolínez et al. 2019). We have used the initial conditions of the reference N -body simulation (the SLICS simulation) Harnois-Déraps et al. (2018), down-sampled to a lower resolution and evolved it using Augmented Lagrangian Perturbation Theory (Kitaura & Hess 2013). This approximated density field is accurate enough at scales of $\sim 4h^{-1}$

Figure 21. Galaxy marked correlation in real $\mathcal{M}(r)$ and redshift space $\mathcal{M}(s)$. Top panel show the result of using the halo virial mass as the mark. Middle panel uses the velocity dispersion and the third shows the results of using the the cross-marked correlation function.

Mpc to robustly study the bias relation between the cosmic web and the halo number counts. The remaining biases introduced by the approximate gravity solver at scales above the mesh resolution are automatically taken into account in the effective bias extracted from the reference simulation. In particular, the approximated density field (used along with the corresponding halo catalog) reference N -body simulation to iteratively learn the halo-bias and a kernel, which are the main outputs of the learning phase of the method. We have shown how the characterization of the halo bias as a function of cosmic-web types and the implementation of a number of realizations as training data set (so as to increase the effective volume of the reference simulation) can generate ensembles of independent realizations of halo number counts with accurate (2–5%) precision in the two and three-point statistics, and its corresponding covariance matrices.

We have described a procedure to assign halo coordinates, velocities and intrinsic properties, aiming at generating a set of 760 dark matter halos, with the same number properties of the reference set. We have assigned velocity dispersion and virial mass following a hierarchical and multi-scaling approach (see § 3.5) designed to replicate the abundance as a function of these properties. The halo two-point statistics replicates that of the reference ones with 5% precision at $k \sim 0.4h\text{Mpc}^{-1}$, which is the maximum wave-number adopted by the DESI mock-challenge. We have verified that covariance matrices of the two and three point statistics measured from the mock catalogues generated by BAM are in very good agreement with those obtained from the reference N -body simulation. Based on these set of halo catalogs, we have generated the same number of galaxy catalogs using an HOD prescription aimed at replicating the abundance of emission-line galaxies. It is important to stress, that the same HOD parameters were applied to BAM as to the N -body based halo catalogs. The goodness of the suit of mocks is assessed not only in Fourier space, but also in configuration space through the correlation function and the marked correlation function.

Despite of the good performance of the method in terms of the different statistical probes explored, we have identi-

fied a number of items in which BAM has to be improved to reduce the deviations observed with respect to a reference simulation. These are

- *Peculiar velocities.* Along with the density-dependent bias correction (described in §3.4), the small-scale clustering signal in redshift-space demands further treatment of the peculiar velocities. This treatment starts with a thorough analysis of the velocity assignment specially for random tracers, as shown in Fig. 8. Generalizations of such an approach to take into account halo properties and/or modification of the full population (dark matter and tracers) are part of this task. A deeper understanding of the origin of the different corrections in the velocities applied in this work is to be addressed in forthcoming publications.

- *Assignment of halo properties.* A thorough approach to this task can be that of imposing the pair-distribution of tracers as a function of the different halo properties. This, however, is a highly expensive task. Although the multi-scale algorithm described in §B is an improvement with respect to previous algorithms, further improvements need to be implemented. To that end, we are currently including a second learning phase and using marked statistics as main diagnosis. The goal is to replicate the clustering pattern observed in the reference as a function of all halo properties.

In general, an accurate performance of BAM does not only depend on these planned improvements. It is also complemented by the characteristics of the reference simulation used as training data set. The SLICS, with a relatively small cosmological volume and initial conditions generated from Gaussian randoms fields, is highly prone to cosmic variance. This is reflected in the limited statistical information contained in a halo-bias obtained from only one reference which in turn can lead to inaccuracies in the generation of halo mock catalogs with different seeds. To take this into account, we pushed the method to the implementation of more than one reference simulation (see Eq. 15) as training data set.

In appendix C we have motivated the implementation of reference simulation based on initial conditions with suppression of cosmic-variance (fixed amplitude initial conditions) (see e.g. Angulo & Pontzen 2016; Chuang et al. 2019; Maion et al. 2022) covering larger cosmological volumes. This scenario can substantially improve the accuracy in the two- and three-point statistics, as well as the procedure to assign halo properties. Such set-up will also allow the method to extrapolate the generation of mock catalogs to volumes larger than that of the reference.

The present paper demonstrates the potential of BAM to speedily deliver halo mock catalogs, with a number of properties, flexible and accurate enough, to implement any mechanism to generate galaxy samples within the context of the halo model. The next step is the generation of larger sets of halo mock catalogs (larger cosmological volumes and light cones) with more halo properties (e.g. spin, concentration, maximum circular velocity) on which different methods for galaxy occupation and selection functions can be imposed to replicate the sky observed by different experiments.

DATA IN THIS ARTICLE

The data underlying this article will be shared on reasonable request to the corresponding author.

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APPENDIX A: HIERARCHY OF PROPERTIES

To motivate the hierarchical property-assignment, we compute the Pearson correlation coefficient using the local dark matter density, virial mass and velocity dispersion, obtained in bins of local density and in different cosmic-web types. The results, shown in Fig. A1, conclude that i) the correlation between halo properties in different cosmic-web types (panel (a)) follows a similar trend in low and intermediate densities, reaching a maximum at $\delta_{\text{dm}} \sim 0$, to then decrease towards high-densities, where the correlation in knots becomes significantly dominant as compared to that in filaments; ii) the correlation between velocity dispersion and dark matter displays (panel (b)) higher values, $\sim 30\%$, specially at high densities, and iii) the correlations between virial mass and local density (panel (c)) are rather weak, with $\leq 15\%$ on average over the density range, and no strong dependence with the cosmic-web type. Notice that the underlying dark matter density field used to compute these correlations is an approximated version of the original field (which has 512 times more particles) whose dark matter particles are used to define these

Figure A1. Pearson correlation coefficients between halo properties (panel a), the local dark matter density with halo virial mass (panel b) and velocity dispersion (panel c), measured in bins of local density for different cosmic-web types, as obtained from the SLICS reference simulation. The error bars denote the standard deviation obtained from the set of catalogs.

halos. Hence, these measurements must not be taken as general claims on the behavior of halo properties, but instead a characterization of the current set-up within the BAM machinery. With this in mind, we adopt it as the main property to start the assignment procedure.

APPENDIX B: MULTI-SCALING ASSIGNMENT

One key aspect to take into account when sampling the halo number counts field with discrete tracers is, on one side, the need to preserve the large scale clustering pattern according to that of the reference, and on the other hand, to avoid halo-exclusion (see e.g. Porciani & Giavalisco 2002; Baldauf et al. 2013; García & Rozo 2019). The former is ensured by an appropriate choice of the gravity solver, while the latter can be addressed at the moment of assigning properties. To that aim, we have envisaged a *multi-scale assignment scheme*, in which a given property (in this case, the velocity dispersion) is assigned in an ordered fashion ensuring that the highest values are linked to tracers far enough to avoid exclusion (see also Zhao et al. 2015, for an early approach). Let us briefly describe the steps designed within the BAM algorithm to assign halo properties:

Figure A2. Top panels: Power spectrum $P(k)$ obtained from learning phase (§2.7) (solid lines) compared to the same statistics from the reference (dashed lines). Colors indicate different snapshots of the UNIT simulation, ranging from $z=0$ (red, upper curves) up to $z=3$ (violet, bottom curves). The outputs and references at each redshift have been both shifted by the same amount to facilitate the comparison. The middle panel shows the kernel \mathcal{K} and bottom panels show the relative residuals in the power spectrum at the different redshifts, using the *normal* (filled circles) and the *phase-inverted* (filled squares) as training set.

(i) We randomly select one reference halo catalog and define a threshold σ_{th} , above which the multi-scaling assignment will be performed.

(ii) For values of velocity dispersion above the threshold σ_{th} , divide the σ_v -range probed by the halo population in \mathcal{N} intervals. Each of these intervals is defined by a minimum

Figure A3. Halo power spectra of $N_{\text{sim}} = 400$ BAM-UNITSim-mock catalogs (grey lines) at different redshifts, obtained from the assignment of number counts. In each panel the colored lines represents the power spectrum of the reference halo catalog at the respective redshift.

and maximum value of velocity dispersion, $\sigma_v^\ell \in [\sigma_v^{\text{min}}, \sigma_v^{\text{max}})_\ell$ ($\ell = 1, \dots, N$).

(iii) Let N_ℓ denote the number of tracers read from one reference simulation in each of these intervals. We construct a number of N spatial meshes covering the cosmological volume of the BAM mocks, each of which is characterized by N_ℓ cells, such that, on average, each cell is populated by one halo within the corresponding interval of σ_v .

(iv) Select a number \tilde{N}_{ref} of reference halo catalogs. This number can be smaller than the figure used for the generation of halo number counts (i.e., $N_{\text{ref}} = 27$). For the current set-up, we have randomly selected $\tilde{N}_{\text{ref}} = 5$ from the available set of SLICS catalogs.

(v) From the set of \tilde{N}_{ref} catalogs, identify the values of velocity dispersion $\{\sigma_v\}_\ell(\{\Theta\}_{\text{ref}})$ as a function of the dark matter properties $\{\Theta\}_{\text{ref}}$. Sort these values top-down in each bin of $\{\Theta\}_{\text{ref}}$ for all values above the minimum threshold σ_v^{th} .

(vi) Proceed to the assignment of properties read from the reference to tracers in a BAM halo catalog. The assignment starts with the interval containing the higher values of σ_v (this mesh is the less populated).

(vii) Loop over the N_ℓ cells in the mesh built over the BAM mock. In each step of this loop, the algorithm randomly selects one fiducial cell (i.e., defined by the nominal resolution 192^3). To avoid the assignment of properties to tracers in adjacent cells, we previously randomized the order of the N_ℓ cells.

(viii) Using the dark matter field of the current mock catalog, we identify the corresponding set of properties $\{\Theta\}_{\text{mock}}$ of the chosen fiducial cell.

(ix) We randomly choose one mock-tracer in that fiducial cell (if any) and assign to it a value of σ_v from the list $\{\sigma_v\}_\ell(\{\Theta\}_{\text{mock}} = \{\Theta\}_{\text{ref}})$. Given that this list is sorted, the first assignment (i.e., first step in the loop over the N_ℓ -cells) will correspond to the largest value of σ_v in the reference catalog.

(x) Repeat the full loop until the number of requested tracers in the level are assigned with properties.

This procedure is repeated for the different levels M_ℓ . For values below the minimum threshold, the assignment is performed in the following way:

(i) Randomly select one tracer (without assigned property) from the mock. Identify the fiducial cell where it resides and the corresponding set of properties $\{\Theta\}_{\text{mock}}$.

(ii) Return to the list $\{\sigma_v\}_\ell(\{\Theta\}_{\text{ref}})$ and randomly assign any of the corresponding values still available (i.e., with $\sigma_v < \sigma_v^{\text{th}}$).

Finally, if there are still tracers with no assigned properties (e.g., due to cosmic variance), BAM statistically assigns values of velocity dispersion by sampling the global halo abundance measured from one reference catalog. This last case represents $\sim 5\%$ of the total assignment, depending on the realization. For the current case, we have implemented $N = 3$ levels with thresholds at $\sigma_v^{\text{th}} = 4, 8$ and 10 km/s.

Once velocity dispersion are assigned, we measure the scaling relation $\mathcal{P}(M_{\text{vir}}|\sigma_v, \{\Theta\})$ (using one realization of the reference set) to assign virial masses with

$$M_{\text{vir}}^{ij} \sim \mathcal{P}(M_{\text{vir}}|\sigma_v^i = \sigma_v^{\text{ref}}, \{\Theta\}_{\text{mock}j} = \{\Theta\}_{\text{ref}}). \quad (\text{B1})$$

The scheme can be generalized to any other set of halo property tabulated in the reference catalog (e.g. spin, concentration, maximum circular velocity).

APPENDIX C: FORTHCOMING APPLICATIONS: EXPERIMENTS WITH PAIRED-FIXED AMPLITUDE COSMOLOGICAL SIMULATIONS

We have seen how the cosmological volume probed by the SLICS suit has imposed a limit to the precision and accuracy in the different summary statistics of the BAM halo-catalogs

when learning from one realization. To circumvent that situation, we pushed to learn from more than one reference simulations, effectively increasing the volume of the training set (see §3.1). Such enlargement of the training set yields products (i.e halo-bias and kernel) which are -from a statistical perspective, not compatible, as the averaged kernel defined in Eq. (15) effectively tries to reproduce the behavior from a fixed-amplitude reference -i.e, devoid of cosmic-variance, while the stacked version of the halo-bias fully retains it.

As pointed in §3.1, a more convenient scenario for the calibration procedure and the generation of mock catalogs with BAM is the implementation of *phase-inverted* pairs of large cosmological simulations generated with fixed-amplitude initial conditions (see e.g. Angulo & Pontzen 2016; Chuang et al. 2019; Maion et al. 2022). In this section we present results from numerical tests that, despite of being part of forthcoming publications, aim at motivating the implementation of BAM with that specific type of training sets.

In our context, the advantages of N -body simulations with suppressed cosmic variance are straightforward to justify. On one hand, the calibration with this type of IC's allows the generation of kernels without any uncertainty from cosmic-variance which in turns allows for an accurate extrapolation of this quantity towards smaller wavenumbers, aiming at generating halo catalogs in larger cosmological volumes (while learning from smaller ones). On the other hand, calibrating the method using the set of two-paired simulations (dubbed as the *normal* and the *phase-inverted*) allows us to consistently extract halo-bias, as in Eq. (15), used in conjunction with an average kernel which (being phase-independent) is the same for the set of two paired references. This, complemented with larger cosmological volumes (and high mass resolution) allows to have a good statistical description of the dark matter density field (e.g. Crocce & Scoccimarro 2006; Klypin & Prada 2018), and in general, of the outputs from the learning phase.

To assess the performance of BAM in this scenario, we have used the UNIT simulation (Chuang et al. 2019). This suit is

represented by a set of two pair-fixed realizations in a volume of $1(\text{Gpc}h^{-1})^3$, run with 4096^3 dark matter particles and mass resolution of $1.2 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot} h^{-1}$ and halo catalogs with a minimum (virial) mass of $3.6 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot} h^{-1}$. We use a number of snapshots in the redshift range $0 \leq z \leq 3$ to generate the same number of kernels and halo bias for the normal as well as for the phase-inverted realization. Following the procedure of §2.4, the IC of the UNITsim are down-sampled to a lower resolution -in this case 256^3 . For each of snapshots, a kernel and a halo-bias is produced following the steps of §2.7, based on the TkWEB model of halo-bias (see §2.6). Figure A2 shows the power spectrum, the kernel and residuals at different cosmological redshifts, as obtained after a learning phase. The solid (dotted) lines in the middle panel shows the kernel obtained from the normal (phase-inverted) realizations, while the bottom panel shows also the residuals derived from the process with the two references.

The procedure described in §3.2 is repeated to generate independent halo number counts. A number (~ 1000) of IC's are generated using the FastPM code (Feng et al. 2016) with the same cosmological parameters and input power spectrum as the UNITsim, this time with allowing cosmic-variance in the form of random Gaussian realisations. The same number of approximated dark matter density fields are accordingly generated. Figure A3 shows the power spectrum of a number of halo number counts distribution at different redshifts, compared with the reference power spectrum from (one of the two) paired references. As pointed before, the results from the calibrations of the paired set are used to generate a total bias and an averaged kernel, as dictated by Eq. (15). An exhaustive analysis of the summary statistics from this set of mocks is out of the scope of this paper, and will be presented in forthcoming publications. However, a simple visual analysis of the different spectra at different redshift reveals a good behavior up to the Nyquist frequency (for this set-up, $\sim 0.8 h\text{Mpc}^{-1}$). Forthcoming work will be dedicated to apply the strategy described in this paper using larger simulations such as the Abacus-summit (Garrison et al. 2018).